

The Ecology of the Welfare State: Studying Sarnath Banerjee's *All Quiet in Vikaspuri*

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Abstract: *The depletion of groundwater in the capital region of New Delhi and the consequent community scuffle as depicted in Sarnath Banerjee's graphic novel All Quiet in Vikaspuri is the subject of the paper. The urban ecological crisis is refracted through the prism of the neo-liberal state policy and is seen as the great galvanizer of the mass, hitherto pushed to oblivion by the neo-liberal State and corporates alike, who reckoned the crisis and its perpetrators and resisted them. The ecological theories of 'bioregion' and 'biophilia' are brought in to analyse the community resistance and the role of the State is scrutinized both in terms of its welfare role and its dwindling into a facilitator of the corporate profiteering that has a direct bearing on the ecological catastrophe. The Gaia hypothesis of Lovelock and Margulis, the paper proposes at the end, needs to accommodate the notion of the welfare State to ensure an equitable distribution of the ecological resources and their protection.*

Keywords: Ground water; Unsight; Bioregion; Biophilia; Gaia Hypothesis; Welfare State

In spite of being the land of many rivers, India in its modern days has seen bitter feuds over water that often got the headlines for all the wrong reasons. The international water rivalry over Sindh and Brahmaputra with the western and eastern neighbours respectively has kept Indian foreign policy on its toes over decades. Inter-state water rivalries are also pretty common

with the Cauvery water dispute often souring the relationships between the southern states of Karnataka and Tamil Nadu and the State regulated dams and their operations like that of the Damodar Valley Corporation and the Bhakra Nangal have caused massive outrage and mass movements in large swathes of the country. Sarnath Banerjee in his graphic novel *All Quiet in Vikaspuri* looks examines the crisis in a more intimate space: the battle over water amongst the citizens of the capital region of the India, New Delhi. It microscopes its lens on what is termed as ‘the community level water war’ that plagues the lives of the citizens in the national capital region and makes violence an everyday phenomenon in the culture, geography and the existence of the urbanscape of the Delhites (Calamur).

Banerjee’s graphic novel captures the water crisis in urban India and connects it with the contours of a greater crisis engendering out of the neoliberal State policies that India toed from the final decade of the previous century. The issue of the groundwater crisis and the consequent reduction of the neighbouring communities into warring tribes is refracted through the prism of macro politico-economics. The novel opens with the details of the small town of Tambapur where the Government run public sector unit of Bharat Copper Limited has its plant. The welfare state run unit not only focuses on the productivity and the profitability of the factory and mines but prioritizes the all round development of the employers and their families as well as the environment of the industrial township. However, with the new wave of liberalization, privatization and globalization takes centertage in India’s economic policy making, the global fluctuation in copper pricing started affecting the plant and its profits. The ministry of disinvestment had the easiest way out of the crisis. As one of the panels in the Banerjee’s work has it; the disinvestment minister raises his forefingers and announces the one pill cure all remedy: ‘PRIVATISE’ (Banerjee 7). What followed was the multinational takeover and a brutal reduction in welfare spending and a crass disregard for the environment and the people of the erstwhile blossoming industrial town. As profits soared for

the multinational, the workers were seen joining an exodus away from Tambapur to join an ever-increasing retinue of unorganized labourer in adjoining metropolises. In their place new contract workers were recruited from afar with little to no commitments of social security extended to them.

One such ill-fated laid off plumber Girish came to New Delhi only to find that severe water crisis has overwhelmingly taken over the capital city of India as has the employment crisis for the likes of him as the city is flooded, not with ample potable water but a sea of unorganized labourers such as him. The novel, at this point, takes a critical turn towards localizing a severe environmental crisis. Tambapur, the site of the factory town, as the story progressed ceased to be a mere geographic space for the likes of Girish. With settled home, aspirations, entertainments, disappointments and desires it appeared to him more like what Robert L. Thayer would term as 'bioregion': Thayer defines the term as 'life-space', a locale where the human, other-than-human and the non-living cohabit to generate an idiosyncratic human culture (Thayer 3). Therefore, whenever Girish is reminded of his good old Tambapur days, memories of not only the space but its vegetation, people and his affective association with them coagulate into a singular recollection that at times appear to him as some kind of trick that his mind is playing on him (Banerjee 16). The bioregion of New Delhi, however, is completely contrary to that of Tambapur. The narrative in graphic is effectively employed here. Banerjee's panels of the blooming days of Tambapur hardly have a loner or an isolated individual, signifying the camaraderie and the bonding that the chronotope of Tambapur in its heydays boasted of. On the contrary, the panels of Delhi are full of lonesome individuals either mired in or battling away battling away unemployment, corruption or an insensitive system. Be it Girish himself waiting by the roadside looking for freelance plumbing employment, the elderly man waking up an hour before daybreak to switch on the booster pump or the panels introducing the corrupt Rajan or Miss Carrey who is relaxing by her compound pool and cannot care less about the depleted groundwater – all are

panels highlighting loners engaged in their private pursuits of persistence, profits or pleasure.

If the marked difference between the two bioregions is in the sheer disconnectedness, then that has further theoretical imports in the ecocritic space. While Tambapur's memory is always of community oriented gregariousness, the space of Delhi is manifested with disconnectedness, distrust towards neighbour and surviving in isolated habitats. Evidently, the two bioregionalism of both spaces are distinctly different. The genealogy of this distinction is not obscure at all. While the first had the lineage in the morale of the welfare state, the second is the aftermath of the times when the State shrunk and profiteering started determining the contours of georgics of economy and politics of the nation. Banerjee's work thus points at a deeper crisis in the theory of bioregion itself. While one bioregion may be profoundly syncretic with the environment, some other may turn out to be painfully alienated from the subjectivity of the being and the environment. Kirkpatrick Sale in his *Dwellers in the Land: The Bioregional Vision* is specific about this alienation and the genesis of the same. He acknowledges the paradigm of bioregion and in its ideal stratum that accommodates "rocks under our feet, the source of the waters we drink, the common insects, birds, mammals, plants and trees; the particular cycle of the seasons" (Sale 42). What Sale recognizes is the shrinkage that this exhaustive compass of bioregion has suffered in the hand of what he terms as 'the industrio-scientific paradigm'. The profit driven capitalist system of production with little to no concern for the welfare economics reduces the individual to the strict squares of productivity and profitability; losing in the process the essential connect with the biotic and abiotic environment that one is intimately connected with.

Banerjee's novel is vivid in its depiction of this rapid shrinkage of the bioregion of the neo liberal state of India. Be it the post privatization unraveling of the township of Tambapur, the graphic references to the build up towards the establishment of the

steel factory on the banks of the Jatadhari river in Odisha or the description of the establishment of the Uttarakhand hydel project that polluted thirty to forty tributaries of the Ganga – the novel continually emphasizes upon the gross disregard that the profit motif nurtures towards anything beyond the anthropocentric in general and the neo-liberal capitalism in particular. In fact, this reduction of the human bioregion, the novel records, has its ill impact on the hermeneutics of individual decisions and macro policy formulations. Banerjee terms this ‘short termism’ and catalogues a series of such pronouncements that ranges from sliding down the banister to save time and dangerously falling off in the process to setting up dams on rivers that destroy communities in order to produce ‘unjustifiably low amounts of electricity’ (Banerjee 56).

The consequence of this myopic approach that prioritizes technocracy and profit over and above everything else, the novel quite rightly depicts, creates a sea of dispossessed who are forced to migrate, lose habitat and lead a life marked by severe vulnerability. Be it the workers who had to leave Tambapur, the contractual workers employed to replace them with crass disregard for labour laws or the inhabitants of the warring colonies of the capital city who are robbed off their basic right to have access to clear drinking water and are forced to literally fight for the same among themselves – all emerge as blood cousins of whom Rob Nixon terms as ‘unimagined communities’ (Nixon 151). Nixon explains that such communities are created when the violence and displacement of people affected by mega dam like large-scale developmental projects are rendered invisible or removed from national and global cultural narratives. These communities are both physically displaced and *imaginatively evacuated* from the consciousness of dominant publics. In *All Quiet in Vikaspuri* such unimagined communities are shown to be no longer on the fringe any more but even the populaces of the highly urbanized elite ghettos of a capital city are made subjected to the same. There remains a distinction, however, between the dispossessed unimagined communities of Tambapur,, Nyamgiri, Kalahandi or

Jharia – the reference of whom are catalogued in a full page panel of the novel (Banerjee 67) and the middle to upper middle class urban dwellers of Shahpurjat, Indraprasth or Shalimar Bagh. The former are turned into oblivion by the high and mighty by their ceaseless pursuit for profit while the latter were at first lulled into the comfort of being the privileged elite only to wake up to the harsh reality that the ecological crisis spares no one as their taps dry out and water became a commodity to fight to the teeth for.

Precisely herein, Banerjee’s novel echoes the spirit that has been valorised by the practioners of the cli-fi or climate fiction in the twenty first century. China Mieville’s *The City and the City* (2009) records the coexistence of two fictional neighbouring cities, namely Beszel and Ul Qoma, whose inhabitants had been taught for ages not to recognize or acknowledge each other’s presence. The economic fortunes of the two cities swing in the classical capitalist boom-bust cycles and a portion of citizens of both the towns recognise that the elements of nature and animals like ‘pigeons, mice, wolves, bats’, spread across both the spaces do not abide by the human dictum of ‘unsight’ or non-recognition of each other (Mieville 112). In *All Quiet in Vikaspuri*, the practice of ‘unsight’ is more intimate as the inhabitants of the same city derecognize the dispossession and hardships of their fellow citizens, thanks to the unequal distribution of social wealth that has soothed the conscience of the former into some sort of social amnesia. Hence, Banerjee depicts the dwellers of the Vikaspuri high rises cannot care less about the source of their buildings’ water supply or the destination of the waste that they generate. For everything they have the smug assertion: “the building provides it” (Banerjee 49). While on the other part of the city, the Yamuna chokes, “sad, sluggish and thick with industrial effluents” (Banerjee 59).

What Banerjee’s work is conspicuous in highlighting is the consequence of the retreating of the welfare state. The disintegration and demise of Tambapur becomes a metaphoric commentary in the novel on silent receding of that system of

governance and its effect on the most vulnerable class of citizens. The novel ups the ante in the later pages as it reaches its central crisis in the narrative: the effect of the withdrawal of the welfare State on the urban middle class, who have been traditionally considered to be the amongst the most vociferous champions of the of the celebrated LPG (liberalization, privatization, globalization). The warring tribes of the urban Delhi are unmistakably hailing from this stratum and it is the depletion of the groundwater, the contamination of river, the overflowing sewers that finally make them realize that the State is no longer there to either provide or protect. Hence what ensues is a twofold privatized undertaking: the Rastogi search for the lost Saraswati with the aim strictly on the control of the last source of water in the city; and the marauding civil war among the citizens of the national capital with the desperation to attain as much access as possible to the basic natural resources for survival even it means killing each other.

However, it is this Girish's search being commissioned by Rastogi for the lost Saraswati that offers an uncanny way out of this crisis of alienation. As Girish drills on, he meets several people who reside in the subterranean quarters beneath the capital city. They are a disparate lot ranging from erstwhile corrupt bureaucrat, ex-army man, wife of a foreign consulate official and so on. They are, however, united by the ecological crisis of the depleted groundwater. As Girish drilled deeper, their marked misanthropy and sheer disgust for the people above is apparent. Banerjee is deft in projecting the 'unimagined communities' in this way. The unremembered surplus population thus emerges as the new class altogether; divided by income stratum, social stratification and economic vulnerability but united by the ecological crisis. As the water crisis start affecting one and all, Banerjee's work as if prophecies, the conventional hierarchies would collapse and telescope all into what Guy Standing would perhaps call the ecological precariat, marked by environmental vulnerabilities born in the wombs of globalization (Standing). Hence the corrupt Awasthy, the carefree Carrey Jones, the grey market operator Tanker Rajen or the prim Lt. Col. B.K. Gambhir

would later on find a natural camaraderie with who may be referred to as the water have-nots of the city once they fight against the water mafia Rastogi's men at the source of Saraswati.

There is always the other side of the 'haves' in the story that records the narrative of inequality in the neo-liberal system of state administration. Like their hapless counterparts who lose everything starting from habitat to groundwater, the haves will also have layers about them, differentiated in a hierarchy of benefits that they derive from their exercise of exploitation. Banerjee here interestingly chooses a representative of a nuanced stratum: Varun Bhalla, the intermediary technocrat who assists the capitalists to takeover state-run enterprises, set up factories and industry units in environmentally sensitive spots, locating opportunities of profit for his capitalist masters at the cost of literally everything and making windfall gains for himself in the process. What the novel shows is that in spite of all his professional success, Varun remains a terrible loner as guilt of displacing thousands in order to drive home his projects gnaws him away in private; so much so that he gradually recedes from his regular professional assignments into binge drinking and weird hobby of costume designing with continual hallucinations of the damages his success has caused to the environment and innumerable human beings. This feeling of shame, according to Sara Ahmed, works in a fascinating twofold way. While the feeling of shame makes one painfully aware that what he has done is terrible and hence he must hide himself from the rest; the feeling simultaneously keeps on making one conscious of being exposed in the most unexpected turns. Hence, Ahmed says, the subject in shame would make erratic to and fro between running away from the site of guilt and rediscovering the wounds of it every now and then and thereby admonishing himself (Ahmed 104).

Bhalla's guilt trip, interestingly, runs parallel to the recipe for resistance that Banerjee proposes in his work. This runs in a twofold way as well. While being isolated and alienated by the designs of the neo-liberal economy, the subjects would at first find

themselves either resigned to this state of alienation, taking it as their inextricable damnation or finding this seclusion to be even desired. However, soon this would seem too much for all and the ecological crisis of depleting to non-existent groundwater calibrates them into an uncanny unity. The hideout of the subterranean Delhi becomes the veritable battlefield of guerilla warfare where a hidden Phillippa or the recluse Col. Gambhir unite against Rastogi's army, thereby establishing an unprecedented unity among the commoners above and below. The ecological crisis and the consequent resistance thus finally galvanize the mass into people.

This marks a clear graduation from Thayer's notion of bioregion as it incorporates within it what Sara Ahmed would term 'economy of affect' (Ahmed 15). Here the emotional affects circulate within the society and state mechanism generating a surplus of response that often catches the power structure off guard. The have-nots of the Vikaspuri refused to slip their bioregion from their fold to the control of the ensemble of a neo-liberal state and corporate behemoths. Precisely herein the mere reference to bioregion transcends to the affective terrain of what E.O. Wilson would call 'biophilia' and Yi-Fu Tuan would term 'topophilia': the feeling of oneness with all living forms of the space and in turn, "an affective bond between people and place or setting" (Thayer 4). This brings the narrative of Banerjee closer to the Gaia hypothesis formulated by James Lovelock and Lynn Margulis. The hypothesis proposes that the earth is at once a sentient and self-acting system in which all organisms – living or non-living – are intimately connected to attain and maintain optimal condition of living (Lovelock). The people of Vikaspuri who are projected so far as not only self-centred but so hateful to each other that the water crisis brought them to kill one another, now fight unitedly against their oppressor in order to maintain the talismanic optimum living condition.

Still Banerjee's narrative remains one of moderate optimism and not a whole hearted clarion call to the dawn of a new

dawn of sorts, even after the popular uprising that it depicts. The system apparently has not changed much and the miraculous quick fix of the discovery of Saraswati, the readers would more or less agree, evidently would not last long. What Banerjee emphasises is the absence of this desired system: one that would ensure a somewhat equitable distribution of natural resources and the social wealth while warranting a fair access to education, upliftment and employment to the citizens. The memory of Tambapur reminds us that this system is the good old welfare state. At the end of the narrative, the State resurface obliquely as we are told that Rastogi is duly imprisoned in Tihar but it is evident that the State is not doing much to protect the sources of water or ensure its proper distribution. It would not be surprising if water mafias are waiting in the fringes, patiently looking for the dust of public fury to settle down before they make their move with someone like Varon Bhalla as their broker.

With his loud silence on critical issues such as these, Banerjee's excellent craft as if incorporates the welfare state itself in the scheme of the biophilia. The retrogression of the State in neo-liberal economy has proven to be disastrous to the people and the environment alike. The mass movements as the one of Vikaspuri would, in Banerjee's design, at best would remain a documented uprising and not one that would cause any fundamental shift since there are miles to go before the citizens recognize the significance of the welfare state in the design of their topos and ecology.

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